

2025

A PICTURE OF THE NATION

ISRAEL'S SOCIETY AND ECONOMY IN FIGURES

Avi Weiss

TAUB CENTER

FOR SOCIAL POLICY STUDIES IN ISRAEL

A PICTURE OF THE NATION

Israel's Society and Economy in Figures

2025

Avi Weiss

Taub Center for Social Policy Studies in Israel
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The basis for many of the figures and analyses in this booklet can be found in the *State of the Nation Report 2024* and other Taub Center publications

Taub Center for Social Policy Studies in Israel

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Foreword

It is my great honor to present the *A Picture of the Nation* for my tenth time. Unfortunately, as last year, this publication is being released at a time when Israel is still immersed in war — in fact, until recently, in two wars. On June 13, 2025, the Israeli Air Force launched a series of attacks on nuclear facilities and other sites in Iran, and in response, Iran fired daily missile strikes towards Israel. The situation escalated when the United States joined the conflict and attacked several of Iran's key nuclear facilities. The war ended 12 days after it began, and Israel now faces the enormous task of recovering from the damage caused by the missiles. The war with Iran added to the ongoing conflict in Gaza, which began following the Hamas attack on October 7, 2023, and continues to this day. As of the time of writing, 50 hostages are still held in Gaza, at least 20 of whom are still alive.

And yet, we continue with our work. In the following pages, we present data across all the research areas of the Taub Center. We begin with an overview of Israel's macroeconomic situation and complete the picture with an analysis of the labor market. We then present two additional perspectives related to the labor market. The first focuses on the expected impact of artificial intelligence on the labor market, and the second deals with the phenomenon of presenteeism — employees being present at work while sick — and its health and economic implications.

Next, we turn to social services in Israel — welfare, health, and education — and discuss some of the key issues in each of these areas from multiple angles, accompanied by up-to-date data. We then present findings from an Online survey conducted with parents of children aged birth to 6, examining how the war has impacted their personal situation and the situation of their young children. In the environment and health sector, we address issues such as the waste crisis and tree cutting for the construction of new neighborhoods. The section on demographics, which concludes the booklet, discusses population growth in Israel and its implications, and presents interesting data on two key demographic components — fertility and migration. Naturally, in several areas, you will find references to the wars and their impact on Israel and its population.

We hope that the war in Gaza will also come to an end soon, that the Iranian nuclear threat will be removed, and that all the hostages will be returned and can begin the process of recovery and rehabilitation.

I am confident that this booklet, with the important findings it presents, will assist decision makers and the general public, and will serve as a valuable resource for all its readers.

Prof. Avi Weiss

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Professor of Economics, Bar-Ilan University

Macroeconomic Trends

The war that began in October 2023 has left a deep impression on the Israeli economy. Remarkably, the economy's resilience has once again been on display. While there has certainly been a significant price paid for the wars in Gaza, in Lebanon, and in Iran, signs suggest that the bulk of the effect can be absorbed within a reasonable amount of time. This, however, necessitates that proper steps be taken by the government to move the economy in the right direction and return Israel to its successful pre-war path.

The following pages present some of the war's effects on the country's economy.

Israel's wartime economy

In the graph: The graph shows the change in GDP and its components in each quarter since the outbreak of the war, compared to the same quarter the previous year, in constant prices and seasonally adjusted.

The sharp decline in GDP in Q4 2023 was driven by a steep drop in investment and private consumption, partially offset by a significant increase in public consumption. In the first three quarters of 2024, GDP contracted relative to the same quarters in 2023 before the war — mainly due to continued declines in investment.

By contrast, in Q4 2024, GDP grew compared to the same quarter in 2023, despite the war in the North. The main reason was a relative recovery in private consumption (around 50% of GDP) and investment (around 25%). In particular, the rebound in investment offsets much of the steep decline recorded in the same quarter of 2023. Public consumption remained at the elevated level reached in the quarter the war began. In contrast to the negative growth of the first quarter of 2024, when Israel continued the ground campaign in Gaza while absorbing missile fire in the North by Hezbollah, in the first quarter of 2025, a rebound continued that began in the preceding quarter. Despite this, GDP growth was moderate, largely because of something of a slowdown in private consumption.

Change in GDP and its components relative to the same quarter in the preceding year

Percent

Source: Benjamin Bental and Labib Shami, Taub Center | Data: CBS

A fall in GDP and private consumption during the war

Background: The October 7 war broke out about three and a half years after the start of the COVID-19 pandemic.

In the graph: The recovery in GDP following the peak of the COVID crisis in Q2 2020 was rapid and impressive, and by 2022, per capita output had surpassed the level it would have reached under the long-term trend (1995–2019). In 2023, even before the war, this exceptional growth slowed, and the economy returned to its long-term path. The contraction in output reported for Q4 2023 brought per-capita GDP back to the level of mid-2021 — about 4% below the level that would have been reached under the trend. Per-capita private consumption did not recover to the same extent as GDP after the pandemic, was already declining before the war, and due to slow expected growth in 2025, the gap will increase to about 6% of GDP by year end.

Beyond the graph: The relatively modest recovery in private consumption following the COVID crisis may be linked to only a partial rebound in outbound tourism (in 2022, departures abroad reached 91% of the 2019 level) and to interest rate hikes that began in Q3 2022. The data highlight the indirect costs of the war in terms of lost output and a substantial decline in Israelis' standard of living.

Source: Benjamin Bental and Labib Shami, Taub Center | Data: CBS

A rise in defense expenditures, but not in government civilian spending

Background: The figure distinguishes between civilian and defense uses in government expenditures. Since the majority of civilian expenditures are for individual consumption (e.g., health and education), they are adjusted for increases in the Consumer Price Index (CPI) and population size, while defense expenditures are adjusted only for inflation.

In the graph: Until the outbreak of the war, defense spending (in January 2022 prices) remained steady at NIS 7–NIS 8 billion per month — about NIS 80 billion per year, or roughly 4% of GDP. The war doubled this spending. In contrast, adjusted civilian government spending was quite similar in 2022, 2023, and 2024. Particularly surprising is the similarity between adjusted civilian spending in Q4 2023 and Q4 2022, despite the severe harm to the civilian population at the end of 2023.

Beyond the graph: The war with Iran is estimated to have increased defense expenditures by NIS 10–NIS 20 billion in June. It is worth noting, however, that compensation for war damages paid out from the Compensation Fund (which amounted to around NIS 20 billion before the war with Iran and have increased by another NIS 8 billion since the war) is not included in government expenditure.

Source: Benjamin Bental and Labib Shami, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Finance

A significant long-term change in the level of defense spending

In the graph: Between 1995 and 2023, real defense consumption grew at an average annual rate of 1.8%, while GDP grew at an average annual rate of 3.8%. In real terms (2015 prices), defense consumption rose from NIS 43 billion in 1995 to about NIS 69 billion in 2021, then declined slightly to NIS 65 billion in 2022. As a share of GDP, defense consumption fell from 7.6% in the mid-1990s to about 4.1% in 2022. Following the war, defense spending rose by roughly 1 percentage point of GDP in 2023 and by 4 percentage points in 2024 — an increase of about NIS 100 billion over the two years.

Beyond the graph: Even before the publication of the Nagel Committee's recommendations, the 2025 defense budget stood at NIS 136 billion. The committee recommended increasing the current year's budget by about NIS 6 billion, bringing it to around 7% of GDP — roughly NIS 60 billion more than what would have been spent had the war not occurred. For the decade beginning in 2026, the Nagel Committee recommends increasing the defense budget by NIS 9–NIS 15 billion per year (a total of NIS 133 billion). At present, there are no identified budgetary sources for this increase. It is likely to be financed through a higher deficit and a rising debt-to-GDP ratio — a path that risks undermining Israel's fiscal stability.

Source: Benjamin Bental and Labib Shami, Taub Center | Data: CBS

In the war’s first year, Israel’s risk premium spiked — but has declined since October 2024

Background: A credit default swap (CDS) is the price paid by holders of a bond (including speculators) who wish to insure themselves against the risk that the borrower will default. This price is quoted as a percentage of the insured debt and reflects the level of risk the market assigns to that bond.

In the graph: The graph shows the risk premium on five-year Israeli government bonds. The judicial reform process before the war raised the risk premium from 0.4% at the end of 2022 to around 0.6% on the eve of the war. The war pushed the premium to 1.4%, peaking at 1.6% just before Israel's strike on Iran in late October 2024. Since then, the risk premium has fallen sharply, reaching 0.8% in early March 2025. It rose thereafter, but since the end of the war with Iran, it has been falling.

Beyond the graph: In fall 2024, the credit rating agencies Moody’s, S&P, and Fitch downgraded Israel’s credit rating (Moody’s and S&P by two notches), and have recently warned of possible further downgrades. The rise in the risk premium and the downgrade increase the interest the government must pay on its debt and affect investor confidence in the strength of the Israeli economy.

Source: Benjamin Bental and Labib Shami, Taub Center | Data: World Government Bonds

High-tech investment has not been hurt by the war

Background: In 2023, the high-tech industry employed about 12% of Israeli wage earners aged 25–64, generated roughly 20% of GDP, and accounted for just over 50% of Israeli exports. This impressive success was largely made possible by strong investor confidence in Israeli high tech and significant foreign investment in the sector. Israeli high tech holds a substantial share of the global industry. Investment in the sector in Israel accounts for around 4%–5% of US high-tech investment and about 2%–3% of global investment, while Israel's GDP represents only about 1.6% of US GDP and roughly 0.3% of global GDP.

In the graph: During the COVID crisis, there was a surge in investment, primarily due to the sharp drop in global interest rates. In Israel, the increase was especially steep — from about \$10 billion in 2019 to nearly \$30 billion in 2021. Following the pandemic and the rise in interest rates, high-tech investment fell worldwide. In 2023, investment in Israel returned to its 2019 level, and in 2024, it rose to around \$12 billion. However, there are warning signs: a contraction in startup activity (page 17), a slowdown in high-tech employment growth (page 30), the purported emigration of skilled workers, and an increase in company registrations in the US.

Source: Benjamin Bental and Labib Shami, Taub Center | Data: Dealroom.co; Ernst & Young; IVC

Signs of a slowdown in early-stage high-tech investments since the start of the war

Background: Large investments are directed toward established companies with proven products. However, initial investments in companies at the start of their journey serve as an indicator of investors' expectations of future success prospects.

In the graph: The figure outlines investment data for companies at the idea creation stage (pre-seed) and the initial stage (seed), which involves early development of an idea toward creating a commercially valuable product. The data show a significant increase in the number of seed-stage investments during the COVID-19 period, coinciding with the overall rise in high-tech investments in Israel. The decline in the number of investments in 2023 and 2024 appears to reflect a return to pre-COVID-19 levels. At the same time, the median investment amount for these organizations rose significantly. In the pre-seed stage, the situation is less clear-cut. There is a sharper decline in the number of transactions and a noticeable reduction in the median investment.

Beyond the graph: Since these stages represent the very early development of an idea or product, it is difficult to predict the implications of this change for the future development of mature companies in Israel.

Source: Benjamin Bental and Labib Shami, Taub Center | Data: IVC

GDP per worker equals that in the OECD, but Israelis work longer hours

In the graphs: The figures display real GDP per worker and per hour worked for Israel, the median for the OECD (excluding Israel), and for a group of reference countries (Austria, Denmark, Finland, Netherlands, and Sweden). In terms of GDP per worker, there has been a rapid narrowing of the productivity gap between Israel and the OECD median that began in the mid-2010s, culminating in the gap's closure. Similarly, GDP per worker in Israel went from about 75% of that in the reference countries to about 90% by 2022.

When moving to GDP per work hour, the results are less favorable, mostly because Israelis work longer hours than workers in these other countries. Still, in early 2000s, an hour worked in Israel produced about 75% of the median output per work hour in the OECD, and, by 2022, this had increased to approximately 90%. Relative to the reference countries, it increased from 60% in the mid-2000s to 70% by the early 2020s.

Beyond the graph: Israel is a dual economy, with a high-tech sector that is as productive as elsewhere while the rest of the economy lags behind. The gap is due to human capital, private capital, and public capital falling behind the corresponding levels particularly in the reference countries.

GDP per worker and per work hour in Israel and in other countries

Fixed dollars, 2020 prices

Note: Reference countries are Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Finland, Netherlands, and Sweden.

Source: Benjamin Bental and Labib Shami, Taub Center | Data: OECD

Labor Markets

Much like after COVID-19, the labor force in Israel was able to bounce back quickly from the shock created by the war. The initial harm came from several sources: businesses shut down in the area surrounding Gaza and near the northern border, workers evacuated from their homes in these areas, reservists, and, initially, parents who had to stay home with their children when the schools closed during the first month of the conflict. While there are some evacuees who have still not returned to their homes and to work, and while there are still many who continue to serve lengthy periods in the IDF reserves, for the most part, the labor market has returned to where it was prior to the war.

In the following pages we survey the situation in the Israeli labor market, including employment and unemployment rates, work hours and wages. We also take a look at the high-tech industry from both an employment perspective and at wages, comparing them to wages outside of this industry.

Once again — a quick recovery in the labor market

Background: The standard definition of unemployment is those who are not working but are actively seeking employment. During the COVID-19 pandemic a new measure, the *broad unemployment rate*, was created to include furloughed workers and those absent due to COVID-related reasons. Post-pandemic, the more inclusive definition was further expanded to include employees temporarily absent from their workplace due to *economic reasons*, e.g., absence resulting from layoffs or business closures.

In the graph: Between January and September 2023, the narrow unemployment rate averaged 3.5%. Rates in the other components of the broad measure were negligible — each averaging under 0.5 percentage points. With the outbreak of the war, the broad unemployment rate surged nearly 6 percentage points, reaching 9.6% in October 2023, a level not seen since March 2021. Temporary absences remained high in the war's early stages due to extensive reserve mobilization, but dropped significantly by the beginning of the year. However, the share of nonparticipants who had either given up on job searches or stopped working due to layoffs or business closures increased compared to the previous year, and stood at 0.9% (versus 0.5% in 2023). At the same time, the narrow unemployment rate fell to 3% on average — about half a percentage point lower than in 2023. In addition, from January to May 2025, the narrow unemployment rate fell to a historic low of 2.8%.

Unemployment rate

Note: The rates shown are relative to two different populations. The blue bars represent the rate among the labor force, while the yellow and orange bars represent the rate among the non-labor-force population.

Source: Michael Debowy, Gil Epstein, and Avi Weiss, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Reserve duty affected industries differentially

In the graph: The figure breaks down the labor market absences by economic sector. The highest rate was observed in the infrastructure sector, where nearly one in six employees was absent due to reserve duty. In the management and support and high-tech sectors, about 10% of employees were called to reserve duty. Notably, there was a phenomenon of partial work absences due to reserve duty, in which mobilized employees continued to work alongside their military service. This was most prominent in the high-tech sector, where nearly 1% of employees continued to work — in some capacity, though not fully — while serving in the reserves.

Differences in reserve duty rates across sectors stem from worker demographics. Certain sectors have a higher proportion of young workers or non-Haredi Jewish men, who make up the majority of the reserve duty population. The yellow diamonds in each column show the adjusted absence rate after accounting for age, gender, and worker sector demographics. As shown, high recruitment rates in infrastructure sectors are partially explained by these demographics, though even after adjustment, recruitment in these sectors remains the highest.

Share of the workforce absent due to reserve duty

Workers under age 50, by economic sector, October–December 2023

Source: Michael Debowy, Gil Epstein, and Avi Weiss, Taub Center | Data: CBS

High employment rates for Israeli women relative to the OECD

In the graph: An international comparison between Israel and OECD countries shows that, in the last decade, Israel has enjoyed a significant advantage of several percentage points in the overall employment rate (ages 15+). This advantage is primarily due to much higher employment rates among Israeli women compared to their counterparts in other high-income countries while the employment rates for men are similar.

Source: Michael Debowy, Gil Epstein, and Avi Weiss, Taub Center | Data: OECD

Men’s work hours fell during the war, but women’s did not

In the graph: In recent years, and more so since the outbreak of the war, the average weekly working hours for Jewish men has decreased. Since October 2023, non-Haredi and Haredi men worked, on average, 5% and 3% fewer hours, respectively, than in the same period in the previous two years. In contrast, the number of hours worked by Arab men remained stable in 2024, averaging 39 hours per week, the same as non-Haredi Jewish men (Haredi men worked an average of 33 hours per week).

The average weekly working hours for Arab women increased by 7% compared to the previous two years, reaching 32 hours per week in 2024. The average hours for non-Haredi Jewish women and Haredi women remained unchanged, at 33 and 26 hours per week, respectively.

Source: Michael Debowy, Gil Epstein, and Avi Weiss, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Average wage increase in Israel in 2023 was about half that in the OECD

In the graph: The wage gains in Israel over the past year, while encouraging compared to previous years, are not exceptional when viewed against other high-income countries. The figure shows changes in real hourly wages across OECD countries in recent years, with two bars per country. One bar shows the cumulative change from Q4 2019 to the end of 2023 or early 2024, and the other presents the annual change to the end of 2023 or early 2024 from the same period in the previous year. In the past year, wage growth in Israel was about half of the OECD average, though the cumulative increase since the start of the COVID-19 crisis was nearly five times the average.

Beyond the graph: While Israel stood out with exceptional wage increases during the COVID-19 crisis and its recovery, the moderation of wage growth in Israel over the past two years has allowed other high-income countries to narrow the gap — though only a few have surpassed Israel in this respect.

Percentage change in real hourly wages Selected OECD countries, 2024/2019 and 2024/2023

Source: Michael Debowy, Gil Epstein, and Avi Weiss, Taub Center | Data: OECD

Growth in high-tech services employment has stalled

Background: The high-tech industry is divided into industrial sectors (pharmaceuticals, computers, and transportation equipment) and service sectors (software development and consulting, communications services, information services, and R&D).

In the graph: Unlike employment in high-tech manufacturing, which has remained stable since the early 2010s, employment in high-tech services grew from about 170,000 at the start of the decade to around 290,000 today. This growth came entirely from the software development and consulting sector, which offset a decline in employment in communications services. The surge in employment coincided with a significant increase in high-tech investment during the COVID crisis and stalled once investment flows declined. The large sums injected into the industry continue to support high activity levels, but the drop in investment may lead to a decline in employment in the sector.

Note: The number in parentheses is the industry code.

Source: Benjamin Bental and Labib Shami, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Average high-tech salary — three times the average in other industries

Background: Unsurprisingly, the rise in high-tech employment was driven by rising demand.

In the graph: The wage gap between high tech and the rest of the economy has grown significantly: in 2012, the average high-tech salary was about 120% higher; by 2024, the gap had widened to 180%. The demand for workers in software development and consulting — now about a third of high-tech employees — appears to be a key driver of wage growth, as seen in the parallel rise in their employment and salaries.

Beyond the graph: The wage gap reflects high tech's outsized contribution to output. Although the sector employs 12% of workers, it produces 20% of GDP — meaning productivity is 1.8 times higher than in the rest of the economy. High-tech workers pay, on average, 6.3 times more in income tax than workers in other sectors and contributed about 36% of all wage-based income tax revenue in 2021. These figures underscore the importance of maintaining and expanding high-tech activity, especially in light of growing national security needs.

Average monthly wage in the main high-tech branches and in the other industries

Note: The number in parentheses is the industry code.
Source: Benjamin Bental and Labib Shami, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Some 94% of high-tech workers are non-Haredi Jews, and only a third of them are women

In the graph: Despite the large premium from working in high tech shown on the previous page, despite the fact that women are more than half of the population, and despite the fact that about 60% of college graduates are women, they are greatly underrepresented in high-tech employment, comprising only slightly above a third of high-tech workers. Other groups underrepresented in high tech in Israel are Arabs (men and women) and Haredi men. The percentage of Haredi women in high tech is only slightly lower than their share in the population.

Beyond the graph: The gender division seen here (two-thirds men and one-third women) is typical worldwide.

Distribution of population and high-tech workforce aged 25–66

By gender and population group, 2018–2023

Source: Michael Debowy, Gil Epstein, and Avi Weiss, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Spotlight

AI and the Labor Market

Artificial intelligence is rapidly becoming one of the most transformative technologies of our time, with growing impact on the economy and labor market. To assess AI's capabilities, we used an exposure index based on ChatGPT-4's ability to perform tasks typical of various occupations. Tasks were classified into three categories: those where a large language model (LLM) alone can cut completion time by at least 50% without reducing quality (E1); those requiring the LLM plus other tools, such as image generation, for similar gains (E2); and tasks not exposed to AI. Tasks were then grouped by occupation.

However, exposure alone fails to capture the full impact. AI's effect depends on job characteristics — two equally exposed occupations may experience very different outcomes. In some cases, AI may displace workers; in others, it may enhance performance. To reflect this, the complementarity index assigns each occupation a score estimating how essential human input remains. This helps distinguish between jobs where AI complements human labor and those where it could replace it.

The following graphs look at both aspects — exposure and complementarity — from different perspectives.

Occupational exposure and complementarity of Generative AI

In the graph: The figure presents all occupations in Israel according to their average exposure to artificial intelligence (E1 and E2) and their complementarity level in 2024. Each bubble represents an occupation — its size reflects its share of the labor market, its height indicates what portion of its tasks are exposed to AI, and its horizontal position shows whether AI is expected to replace human workers (left — low complementarity) or to assist and complement them (right — high complementarity). In occupations with low complementarity, AI is likely to replace workers. In those with high complementarity, AI may simply assist — or replace some workers while increasing the productivity of others.

The graph helps illustrate the differences between occupations: for example, primary school teachers and accountants have similar levels of exposure to AI, but their complementarity differs — teachers have high complementarity (AI is less likely to replace them), while accountants have lower complementarity.

Beyond the graph: This aligns with intuition — teachers may use AI for tasks like grading or lesson planning, but their presence is essential for human interaction, education, and maintaining discipline. For accountants, there are fewer aspects of the job that cannot be automated.

Exposure to AI and complementarity in Israel

Ages 25-64, 2024

Source: Debowy et al., Taub Center and Mosaic Institute | Data: CBS

The more educated the workers, the more they are exposed to artificial intelligence

In the graph: We divide all workers in the labor market into five equally sized groups (quintiles) based on the complementarity index, and then calculate the share of workers in each quintile by education level. The gray area shows the share of workers with that level of education in each quintile, while the bars show the exposure of those workers to artificial intelligence. The horizontal line indicates the average exposure by education level.

The graph shows that exposure scores increase consistently with education, but so does the share of workers in occupations with high complementarity. For example, among those at highest risk of replacement (workers in the lowest complementarity quintile), only 16% of workers with a bachelor's degree fall into this group, compared to 30% of workers with a high school education.

Beyond the graph: This finding points to the complexity of analyzing AI's potential impact. The claim that artificial intelligence primarily threatens the most educated workers is not accurate — in some respects, the risk of replacement may be greater for less educated workers, even though exposure to AI rises with education.

Exposure to AI (E1) and highest educational level

Workers aged 25–64, by highest educational degree and complementarity quintile, 2024

Source: Debowy et al., Taub Center and Mosaic Institute | Data: CBS

Exposure and complementarity by gender and population sector

In the graph: Additional insights emerge when breaking down the data by gender and population group. On average, women's exposure to artificial intelligence is higher than men's (0.20 vs. 0.15 on the E1 index, and 0.56 vs. 0.47 on the E2 index). Moreover, men and women are not evenly distributed along the complementarity index, with a high share of women concentrated at the extremes — particularly at the high-risk end. The largest disparities are found in occupations with the highest risk of replacement. For example, over a quarter of women work in occupations where the risk of replacement is highest (such as secretarial work, customer service, and sales), compared to less than one-fifth of men.

These patterns exist across all population groups, but the gender gap is largest in the Arab sector, where women's exposure is twice that of men. However, exposure levels for both men and women in the Arab sector are lower than those of their counterparts in the Jewish sector, across all levels of complementarity.

Exposure to AI (E1) and gender Workers aged 25–64, by complementarity quintile, 2024

Source: Debowy et al., Taub Center and Mosaic Institute | Data: CBS

The probability to be unemployed rises with the level of exposure, except among those with high complementarity

In the graph: Controlling for other factors, we find that an individual's likelihood of being unemployed or discouraged from seeking work increases significantly with greater exposure to artificial intelligence — especially in occupations with low complementarity. On average, a 0.1-point increase in the exposure index corresponds to a 0.02 percentage point decline in employment probability in 2024. Among the bottom four complementarity quintiles, the likelihood of being unemployed or discouraged rises with AI exposure. In the top quintile, by contrast, that likelihood decreases with exposure. In the lowest quintile, a 0.1-point increase in the exposure index corresponds to a 0.04 percentage point drop in employment, while in the top quintile, the same increase is associated with a 0.01 percentage point rise in employment.

The graph also shows the employment likelihood in 2023 and 2024 for workers with average levels of exposure. The change between these years suggests that rising exposure to artificial intelligence contributed to a 0.07 percentage point drop in the likelihood of being employed. In other words, AI appears to have had a negative effect on employment outcomes.

Probability of being unemployed or no longer seeking employment

Workers aged 25–64, by exposure index (E1) and complementarity quintile, 2024

Source: Debowy et al., Taub Center and Mosaic Institute | Data: CBS

Spotlight

Presenteeism

Presenteeism, going to work when sick, has both health and economic costs and benefits.

Health-wise, employees who go to work while ill with contagious diseases risk infecting colleagues, clients, patients, or students, potentially spreading the infection beyond the workplace. However, individuals going to work while ill primarily endanger themselves as it may lead to more severe illness and increase medically-related absences. On the other hand, going to work with a noncontagious illness may allow employees to maintain a professional and social routine, which could even aid in their recovery process.

Economically, health risk factors could lead to costs associated with reduced productivity, including productivity losses due to a slower work pace, professional errors, and safety violations. However, presenteeism could provide benefits at the individual and organizational level; individuals may be perceived as committed employees, which could enhance their status and future promotion prospects. It may also reduce costs arising from hiring replacement workers and alleviate the workload for other employees.

The following are results from the first attempt to examine the extent of presenteeism in Israel and the factors affecting it. Such data were collected only once in Israel (in 2016), but there is no reason to believe that the picture has significantly changed since then.

Over 60% of Israeli workers report showing up at work while sick

Background: Absenteeism is relatively simple to identify and measure. The same is not true of presenteeism since it requires identifying when someone showed up to work, but should not have done so due to illness. Thus, it is dependent on self-reporting.

In the graph: In the Central Bureau of Statistics 2016 Social Survey — the only year in which such data were collected — 61% of employees reported showing up to work while sick. When limiting the sample to employees who were sick at least once during the year, the data indicate that about two-thirds of employees showed up to work while sick at least once.

Beyond the graph: This topic is largely neglected despite having enormous social, health, and economic consequences. According to estimates of the World Economic Forum from May 2020, the economic costs of presenteeism to US firms amounted to some \$226 billion a year.

Extent of presenteeism in Israel
Workers aged 25–64, worker health characteristics, 2016

Note: Excluding those who work from home.
Source: Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Women tend to come to work sick more often than men

In the graph: Controlling for other characteristics, presenteeism is higher among women than among men. It is also higher among the religious and Haredi populations than among other groups. Among the Arab population, presenteeism rates are the lowest. In addition, academic education does not affect presenteeism.

Beyond the graph: Women tend to use more sick days and child sick leave, which contributes to increased absenteeism and thus may encourage presenteeism. Subpopulation differences may reflect cultural differences in how groups from different backgrounds view working while ill, and may also indicate a concern among some employees that their absences will be perceived negatively by employers.

Additionally, presenteeism rates differ across employment characteristics. Higher presenteeism rates are found among male employees with managerial authority. The same holds for those working over 50 hours per week, signifying workaholism or a workplace culture where employees are expected to work long hours. In addition, those with greater autonomy and more substantial challenges at work also tend to have a higher incidence of presenteeism.

Expected presenteeism among workers and socio-demographic characteristics

Workers aged 25–64, 2016

Note: Excluding those who work from home. The horizontal lines at the end of the bars represent the 95% confidence intervals.

Source: Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Better relationships at work tend to decrease presenteeism

In the graph: Workplace relationships play a role in determining presenteeism rates. An increase in the frequency of managerial support and assistance was found to reduce presenteeism. Presenteeism rates among employees who frequently receive support from their managers are estimated to be lower by about 7–10 percentage points compared to those who do not receive such frequent support. This holds across the entire sample of salaried employees and within distinct groups, suggesting the importance of leadership culture in organizational health culture regarding employee well-being.

A toxic work environment, exemplified by exposure to violent behavior, can negatively affect an employee's mental and overall health. For example, presenteeism is expected to be more common among employees exposed to violent behavior at the workplace compared to those not exposed. Presenteeism rates are also higher among salaried employees who felt discriminated against compared to those who did not. Employees who report feeling discriminated against may feel compelled to come to work even when sick out of concern for their status and job.

Expected presenteeism rates and workplace relationships

Note: Excluding those who work from home. The horizontal lines at the end of the bars represent the 95% confidence intervals.

Source: Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: CBS

High level of presenteeism among teachers

In the graph: In a breakdown by economic sectors, presenteeism is more prevalent among employees in hospitality and food services, local administration, public administration and defense, and education (with presenteeism rates of at least 70%). In contrast, employees in transportation and postal services have the lowest presenteeism rates (57%).

Beyond the graph: The education sector has the largest proportion of employees (15%), and presenteeism rates in this sector are among the highest. Presenteeism in the education sector may impact public health when employees are sick with contagious diseases, largely due to the high level of interpersonal interaction between teaching staff and students. At least part of the explanation for the high rate of presenteeism may lie in the high cost of teacher absences, as these affect both the school by disrupting school functioning and making it challenging to find substitutes at short notice and the students through reduced student motivation and academic achievement.

Expected presenteeism rates and economic sector

Workers aged 25–64, 2016

Note: Excluding those who work from home. The horizontal lines at the end of the bars represent the 95% confidence intervals.

Source: Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Welfare

Over the past year, responding to the victims of the October 7, 2023 massacre and the subsequent war has been at the forefront of Israel's welfare and social security systems. This effort has spanned numerous areas of activity and required extensive resources, as well as widespread preparation at both local and national levels. Alongside addressing the consequences of the war, Israel's welfare and social security systems have continued to grapple with longstanding challenges of the welfare state: reducing rates of poverty and inequality; addressing shortcomings in programs like Savings for Every Child, food vouchers, and the work grant; or limitations associated with the centralization of policy making and the relative lack of resources in the welfare system. While steps have been taken to address some of these challenges, the path to achieving significant improvement in Israel's welfare system remains long, as presented in the pages that follow.

A substantial rise in social expenditure

Background: Social spending includes expenditures on social security, health, education, social welfare, and higher education.

In the graph: After two years of reductions in social spending following the peak during the COVID-19 crisis, 2023 saw an increase that reached a new high in 2024. That year, about NIS 404 billion were allocated to social issues. Compared to 2023, this represents an increase of about NIS 48 billion in current prices and about NIS 38 billion in 2024 prices. The main driver of the rise in social spending is higher spending on social security, mainly due to the war and its consequences.

Beyond the graph: Before the COVID-19 pandemic, social spending in Israel was relatively stable at around 18% of GDP. The pandemic pushed it to a peak of 23%. Since then it was reduced, but in the last year it rose to 20% of GDP. The percentage out of government expenditures rose in recent years, reaching 64% in 2022. In 2024, however, due to large increases in government expenditures, this has fallen to around 59%, the lowest level in more than a decade.

Social expenditure in Israel

NIS billion, 2024 prices

Source: John Gal and Shavit Ben-Porat, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Finance; NII

Spending on social services is similar to the OECD average, but lower than in other welfare states

In the graph: When looking only at welfare services — that is, services provided by the government ministries responsible for social services (excluding the National Insurance Institute's benefit system, the education system, and healthcare services) — a clear gap emerges between Israel's welfare state and those of other countries. In 2021, spending on these welfare services in Israel stood at 2.9% of GDP. This rate is relatively close to that of the United States, higher than in Italy, but significantly lower than in countries like Denmark, Sweden, and Norway.

Social expenditure on services as a percent of GDP
2021

Note: The expenditure includes spending on in-kind long-term care, which could not be isolated, even though in Israel such care is mainly provided as cash benefits.

Source: John Gal and Shavit Ben-Porat, Taub Center | Data: OECD

Spending on welfare services per user rises with the socioeconomic ranking of the locality

Background: Funding for the operations of social service departments in local authorities — based primarily on allocations from the Ministry of Welfare and Social Affairs, and to a lesser extent on local government resources — is distributed unequally across local authorities. This has led to significant disparities between localities in the level and accessibility of welfare services.

In the graph: Average annual spending on welfare services per service user in localities in the lowest socioeconomic clusters ranges from NIS 4,596 to NIS 6,685. In the highest clusters, the average is nearly double, ranging from NIS 9,989 to NIS 10,898.

Beyond the graph: These disparities stem from several factors: the matching system used to fund welfare services, which conditions Ministry funding on financial participation by the local authority; differences in the willingness of localities to allocate additional resources to welfare areas; and variation in the costs of different types of services.

Average annual expenditure on welfare per service user
By socioeconomic cluster, NIS, 2021

Source: John Gal and Adi Tarabeih, Taub Center | Data: CBS

The number of unfilled positions for social workers increased during the war

Background: In the weeks and months following October 7, 2023, the Ministry of Welfare and Social Affairs was required to address complex and unexpected situations. To address these demands, the Ministry received budgetary supplements.

In the graph: In response to the new needs created by the war, additional social worker positions were added to social services departments in local authorities. However, as shown in the graph, even during this period, the Ministry of Welfare and Social Affairs struggled to fill these positions. For example, in June 2023, there were 747 unfilled positions, with a staffing rate of 88%. By March 2025, the number of unfilled positions had increased to 1,289, and the staffing rate had fallen to 82%. The increase in unfilled positions primarily reflects the additional positions created in response to the significant rise in needs during the war. The shortage is particularly severe in the evacuated local authorities.

Beyond the graph: The difficulty in staffing social worker positions remains one of the major challenges currently facing the Ministry.

Positions and staffing rates in social service departments

Note: The figure shows only positions funded by the Ministry of Welfare and Social Affairs.
 Source: John Gal and Shavit Ben-Porat, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Welfare and Social Affairs

A dramatic rise in expenditure on victims of terrorism

In the graph: One of the drivers of the increase in social security spending in 2023 was the dramatic rise in expenditures under the Benefits for Casualties of Hostile Acts Law. In the decade preceding October 7, 2023, the number of recognized victims of hostile acts averaged around 5,000 per year. Following the massacre and the war, amendments were made to the law and its regulations to expand eligibility and improve benefit uptake. By October 2024, more than 70,000 individuals had been identified as victims of terrorism, and by February 2025, 22,666 had received formal recognition. As a result, monthly spending on compensation rose significantly — from an average of NIS 51 million in the five years before the war to NIS 261 million in February 2025.

Beyond the graph: Due to these changes and the dramatic expansion in the number of eligible recipients, monthly spending on compensation for victims of hostile acts rose to approximately NIS 480 million by the end of 2023 — nearly ten times the monthly average in 2022 (in 2023 prices). This figure includes grants and initial payments provided by the National Insurance Institute without supporting documentation, as part of the expedited recognition process for victims of terrorism.

Average monthly expenditure on compensation to hostile action casualties

NIS millions, 2024 prices

Note: The figure shows the average monthly expenditure for every year, except in the final columns that relate to specific months after October, 2023.
Source: John Gal and Shavit Ben-Porat, Taub Center | Data: NII

The changes made to the Savings for Every Child program are expected to improve its effectiveness

Background: Under the Savings for Every Child program, the National Insurance Institute deposits NIS 57 per month (as of 2024) into a savings account for each child, and parents may choose to match this amount from the child benefit. Parents can select an investment track from a range of options; if no active choice is made, a default track is assigned.

In the graph: Data from the National Insurance Institute show that in 2023, in at least 33% of accounts, parents did not actively choose an investment track, and the default track was applied. The data also show that about 21% of the accounts were managed in banks, with the remainder in provident funds.

Beyond the graph: In July 2024, two major changes were introduced to the operation of the Savings for Every Child program. First, for children whose parents do not choose an investment track, the default is now a provident fund with a high-risk profile, which is expected to yield higher long-term returns. Second, it is now possible to transfer accounts managed by banks to a provident fund track — an option that was not previously available. These changes are expected to improve the performance of the savings plans.

Distribution of Savings for Every Child plans
Savings track selection, 2023

Source: John Gal and Shavit Ben-Porat, Taub Center | Data: NII

The number of weekly minimum wage work hours needed in Israel to rise above the poverty line is much higher than the OECD average

Background: The most recent poverty data show that between 2020 and 2023, the poverty rate in Israel remained high and relatively stable, at 20.7% of the population. The large number of people living below the poverty line reflects both the limitations of current anti-poverty policy and the difficulty of escaping poverty.

In the graph: One way to illustrate the difficulty of rising out of poverty is to calculate the number of weekly work hours at the minimum wage needed for a household to rise above the poverty line. A comparison with the OECD highlights how difficult this is in Israel: while the OECD average is 57 hours per week, in Israel it takes 70 hours.

Weekly work hours needed to rise above the poverty line
For a family of two parents and two children aged 4 and 6, 2022

Source: John Gal and Shavit Ben-Porat, Taub Center | Data: OECD

Food insecurity in Israel is higher than the average in other high-income countries

Background: Food insecurity is linked to a range of health problems, including diabetes, obesity, cardiovascular disease, respiratory illness, and stroke. It is a significant challenge even in high-income countries. Health impacts may result directly from poor nutrition or indirectly through chronic inflammation and the onset of chronic illness. Even when caloric intake is sufficient, a condition of hidden hunger can arise, characterized by a lack of essential nutrients. Children are especially vulnerable to the effects of hidden hunger, with the most common deficiencies being iron, iodine, vitamin A, and zinc. Food insecurity has also been linked to mental health issues.

In the graph: The prevalence of food insecurity in Israel is higher than the average.

Beyond the graph: Due to the extent of the problem, food insecurity has received growing attention in recent years. The National Council for Food Security has developed a national framework to reduce the phenomenon. In parallel, the Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security is formulating a national food security plan aimed at ensuring long-term food supply for Israel's citizens. The establishment of the National Authority to Combat Poverty in March 2025 threatened the continued existence of the National Council for Food Security, but it was ultimately decided to preserve the council. Nonetheless, sustainable funding for its operations remains necessary.

Share of individuals in moderate and severe food insecurity High-income countries, 2021–2023

Source: Nadav Davidovitch and Natan Lev, Taub Center | Data: Food and Agriculture Organization of the UN

The food voucher program has improved, but is still far from ideal

Background: In 2021, the Ministry of the Interior launched a food voucher program for the first time aimed at assisting low-income families by distributing rechargeable food cards. After the first distribution round, the Taub Center examined the gap between the share of families receiving vouchers and the poverty rate among families in each locality. In light of the study's findings and public criticism from various organizations, several changes were made to the program's eligibility criteria, and a second distribution round took place at the end of 2023 and throughout 2024.

In the graph: A comparison between the two rounds shows that the average gap between the share of families eligible for food vouchers and the share of families living in poverty narrowed somewhat — from 8.2% in the first round to 5.7% in the second. However, an examination by locality group reveals that the changes were not uniform. In Arab localities, the gap narrowed the least; in Bedouin localities, the reduction was more substantial (though the gap remained the largest). In Haredi localities — the only group where the first round showed a positive gap — the gap also narrowed in the second round but remained the only positive gap.

Gap between families qualifying for food vouchers and share of families living in poverty

Source: John Gal and Shavit Ben-Porat, Taub Center | Data: CBS; Ministry of Interior; NII

Health

Due to the ongoing war, Israel's healthcare system remains stretched to its limit, especially in the areas of mental health and rehabilitation. Despite significant needs, national public spending is still among the lowest in the OECD. Nevertheless, the system demonstrates remarkable resilience, and more than a year and a half after the October 7 massacre, the healthcare system in communities and hospitals remains mobilized to address both the consequences of the war and daily challenges.

Despite considerable investment in increasing the number of healthcare workers and expanding quotas for medical students and other health professions — including new roles such as physician associate — there is still a shortage of personnel, particularly in the periphery. This situation contributes, among other things, to an increase in average wait times for certain healthcare services.

The data that follow provide insight into what is happening in Israel's healthcare system, both in terms of system performance and population health and behavior.

The healthcare system is dealing with thousands of hospitalizations due to the wars

Background: Over the past 20 months, the healthcare system has been dealing with a large number of casualties from the wars in various fronts — Gaza, Lebanon, Yemen, and Iran.

In the graph: The highest daily average of hospitalizations due to the wars occurred in October 2023. In November and December 2023, the daily average remained above 100 hospitalizations. In October 2024, after 9 months with a lower daily average, there was an increase in hospitalizations due to intensified fighting with Hezbollah. In June 2025, during the war with Iran, the daily average of hospitalizations was the highest since October 2023.

Beyond the graph: On October 7–8, 2023, 2,061 casualties were hospitalized in Israeli hospitals following Hamas’s surprise attack. This number accounts for 12% of the total general hospitalization beds in Israel. During the 12 days of Operation Rising Lion, more than 3,700 casualties were hospitalized — more than 300 per day on average.

Average daily new hospitalizations since the start of the wars

Note: Data for October 2023 relate to the period from October 7 until the end of the month.

Source: Nir Kaidar, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Health

Wait times for specialists lengthened in 2023, with an improvement in 2024

Background: Wait times for community-based specialist care are an important measure of access to healthcare.

In the graph: Until 2023, average wait times rose in most specialties, but there was a slight drop between 2023 and 2024. Dermatology was an exception, increasing from 34.75 days in Q1 2023 to 36.87 in Q1 2024 and to 44.5 by Q4. Endocrinology and neurology had the longest wait times (about 50 days), while orthopedics and gynecology had the shortest (about 20 days).

Beyond the graph: Use of community-based services is another indicator of access. The 2022 report of the National Program for Quality Indicators in Community Healthcare shows how screening tests are used by health fund members across regions, population groups, and ages. Comparing to 2019 highlights changes since the COVID-19 pandemic. The report shows a decline in BMI checks, smoking status documentation, blood pressure measurement, hemoglobin testing, and osteoporosis treatment rates after hip fractures. It also points to persistent gaps between the center of the country and the periphery.

National average wait times for specialist consultations in the community

Note: Data is presented only for 2022 and onwards in some areas due to the lack of available data for previous years.

Source: Nadav Davidovitch and Natan Lev, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Health

Despite the increase in training of healthcare professionals, a shortage still exists

Background: Israel's healthcare system has been grappling with a worsening workforce crisis in the health professions.

In the graph: The number of licensed nurses and doctors in the public sector aged 67 or younger per 1,000 population remains below the OECD average.

Beyond the graph: The physician shortage is expected to worsen despite the anticipated increase in the number of practitioners. Mental health specialties face particularly severe workforce shortages. In response, special emphasis has been placed on increasing the number of medical students in Israel. Despite the success in expanding enrollment, the number of graduates per capita in Israel was only half the OECD average. In addition, there are some 3,700 physicians currently abroad, and government efforts are invested in bringing them and physician *olim* to Israel. (In 2023, 494 doctors registered as immigrants to Israel, and in 2024, 519 registered. According to data from the *Nefesh B'Nefesh* organization and the Ministry of Aliyah and Integration, the annual average between 2013 and 2018 was about 350 doctors, and since 2019, a gradual increase has been observed.)

Another step taken to address the anticipated shortage has been the suggested development of health professions that can support physicians, such as the physician associate profession (PA). Several PA programs are planned to be opened in the coming academic year.

Active physicians and nurses

Per 1,000 population, 2021–2023

Source: Nadav Davidovitch and Natan Lev, Taub Center | Data: OECD

The incidence of type 2 diabetes is expected to grow more quickly among Arabs than among Jews

Background: By utilizing 2019 age-specific incidence data for different diseases and CBS population projections, we discern the projected number of new cases of type 2 diabetes (T2D, on this page) and ischemic strokes (IS, next page) through 2040.

In the graph: The most rapid rates of increase in new T2D cases in the Jewish population will occur in 2025–2035, when the larger cohorts start to reach peak T2D incidence ages. The number of new cases in the 55–64 age group will increase by around 3% per year in 2028–2032, and fall to 1%–2% per year thereafter. In total, the average rate of growth in 2020–2040 will be 1.52%.

In the Arab population, growth is anticipated to be much higher, driven by a more regular age structure above age 20 and rapid increases in the number of cases below age 50. If current age-specific T2D incidence rates remain constant, the absolute number of new T2D cases in the Arab population will rise by at least 2.8% per year up to 2028 and at least 2.5% per year until 2034.

Projected new cases of type 2 diabetes up to 2040
By age and population group

Note: The estimates are based on prevalence data from the Global Burden of Disease studies for 2019 combined with CBS population projections and assume constant 2019 age-specific incidence rates.

Source: Sadeh, Grotto, Davidovitch, and Weinreb, Taub Center

The number of ischemic strokes is likely to rapidly increase as the elderly population grows

In the graph: Anticipated growth in the absolute number of IS cases outpaces those of T2D. Overall, IS will grow by around 16% every 5 years until 2035 (annualized 2.3% per year), and then by 13% up to 2040. However, that growth will be particularly high at older ages given the much larger cohort of people currently in their early 70s, relative to those in their late 70s. Assuming constant age-specific incidence rates, we will therefore see very rapid increases in the absolute number of new IS cases in the 80–84 age group between 2025–2030 (10.0% per year), and then in the 85+ group from 2030–2035 (7.4% per year).

Beyond the graph: Chances of recovery at these ages are the lowest and costs of care the highest. The rise in stroke cases will lead to higher costs. This increased financial burden will impact both the healthcare system and families of stroke survivors. As with diabetes, the Arab population experience higher stroke rates.

Projected new cases of ischemic stroke up to 2040

Note: Projections assume constant 2019 age-specific incidence rates.
 Source: Sadeh, Grotto, Davidovitch, and Weinreb, Taub Center

As income increases, men smoke less and women smoke more

Background: Between 2015 and 2019, the smoking rate among Israelis aged 16–74 was stable at about 19.5%. It then began to rise steadily, reaching 21.1% in 2023.

In the graphs: The top graph shows that in 2023 the smoking rate among men was 2.2 times higher than among women. Men in the lowest socioeconomic quartile smoked nearly twice as much as men in the highest quartile. Among women, the lowest smoking rate was found in the lowest socioeconomic quartile, while women in the third quartile had the highest rates. The lower graph shows that overall tobacco product purchases decrease as socioeconomic status rises.

Beyond the graphs: Although smoking contributes to chronic illness and harms health, a significant share of Israel's adult population continues to smoke. In 2023, the share of daily smokers in Israel was 16.9% — higher than the OECD average of 13.2%. The steady increase in smoking prevalence and the gaps across socioeconomic groups call for a broad strategy to reduce smoking, with a special focus on narrowing disparities: stronger monitoring, creation of smoke-free public spaces, tighter advertising and marketing restrictions, effective taxation, and more cessation support programs.

Source: Ofir Gonen, Natan Lev, and Nadav Davidovitch, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Household Expenditure Survey; Ministry of Health, National Program for Quality Indicators, selected indicators for 2023

An increase in obesity rates

Background: In recent decades, high-income countries have seen a steady rise in overweight (BMI 25–30) and obesity (BMI over 30) — major risk factors for disease and lower life expectancy and quality of life. This trend is linked to modern lifestyles, including poor diet and lack of exercise.

In the graph: In 2023, 53.7% of Israelis reported being overweight or obese, slightly below the OECD average of 54.2%.

Beyond the graph: In 2023, the share of overweight adults held steady at 33.7%, but obesity rates have continued to rise since 2020. Among 7-year-olds there was a slight decline, but among 14–15-year-olds, rates kept increasing. CBS data for 2023 show that 21% of adults drink at least three sugary drinks a day, 54% eat a sweet snack at least twice a week, and 30% eat a salty snack just as often. The 2023 Youth Risk Behavior Survey (HBSC–WHO) found that Israeli students rank near the bottom internationally for physical activity: only 11% get an hour of daily exercise, and 17% do none at all.

Source: Ofir Gonen, Natan Lev, and Nadav Davidovitch, Taub Center | Data: OECD

A rise in prescriptions for anti-depressants and tranquilizers

Background: Over the past decade, mental health services in Israel have faced severe strain, which worsened with the COVID-19 crisis and the October 7 attack and ensuing war.

In the graph: Recent years show a rise in prescriptions of anti-depressants and tranquilizers. Anti-depressant use is higher than tranquilizer use, and women use both more than men. The increase was especially notable in 2022–2023, mainly among people under age 70. Tranquilizer use rose by 3.5% in this period, and anti-depressant use by 6.3%.

Beyond the graph: Prescriptions for tranquilizers were highest among those in the lower-middle socioeconomic group, while prescriptions for anti-depressants were highest among those in the highest socioeconomic group.

The provision of mental health care in Israel involves a number of agencies. This requires strategic workforce planning and better access to services, with special attention to barriers that cause unequal access and treatment among different population groups. Under the national plan for immediate response in mental health and rehabilitation, a budget of NIS 1.4 billion per year has been set for 2024 and 2025.

Prescriptions of anti-depressants and tranquilizers

Prescriptions per 1,000 population per year

Source: Ofir Gonen, Natan Lev, and Nadav Davidovitch, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Health

Maccabi draws stronger socioeconomic groups, Meuhedet and Leumit draw weaker groups

In the graph: The figure shows the distribution of new members joining each health fund by the socioeconomic ranking of their locality. It clearly indicates that Maccabi Healthcare Services focuses its efforts on recruiting members from stronger populations — the number of new members increases as the socioeconomic ranking of the locality rises. In contrast, Meuhedet Health Services recruits more members from lower-ranked clusters (mostly Haredi). For Clalit Health Services, no significant differences were observed in the recruitment of new members across the various socioeconomic clusters.

Beyond the graph: The Israeli National Health Insurance Law is based on the principle of managed competition among health funds as a means to achieve both efficiency and equity and improve the quality of care and health outcomes. Health funds’ recruitment of new members is one of the main results of this competition that, if not properly regulated, can result in negative results.

Source: Bin Nun et al., Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Health; NII

Net transfer of members into Maccabi Healthcare Services

Background: Israel's National Health Insurance Law, allowing members to transfer between health funds, was passed three decades ago. In the first three years after its passage, transfer rates were high, exceeding 4% annually. Since 1998, there has been a significant decline in transfer rates, which have dropped to around 1% per year. Starting in the early 2000s, there was a slow upward trend in transfer rates, reaching 2.6% in 2021. In recent years, however, transfer rates have begun to decline again, reaching 1.9% in 2024.

In the graph: The first two parts of the graph present the number of people leaving and joining each fund. In the early years of the law, the number of members leaving Clalit Health Services was very high, significantly more than the number leaving other funds. However, since the early 2000s, Clalit has had the highest number of new members. It is important to remember that Clalit is the largest health fund in Israel.

Looking at net transfers provides a different perspective. From 1995 to 2010, Clalit experienced negative net transfers, meaning more members left the fund than joined it. A similar trend has characterized the fund since 2016. From 2015 to 2024, Maccabi Healthcare Services has led in positive net transfers. Leumit Health Services has had a negative transfer balance since 2006, while trends for Meuhedet Health Services have varied over the years.

Trends in member transfers between health funds

Thousands

Note: Net transfers refers to the number of new members joining a fund minus the number of members leaving it.
 Source: Bin Nun et al., Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Health; NII

Education

The graphs that follow focus on the performance of the education system in Israel. We begin by revisiting the question of whether there is a teacher shortage. Instead of the usual examination of teacher numbers and training, we focused on issues that are less commonly discussed but are, in our view, closely related to the perception of a teacher shortage — workplace absenteeism and turnover.

We then look at per-class and per-student budgetary issues in official regular elementary schools, with the exception of Haredi schools. We show that the gaps between the State Hebrew schools, the State-religious schools, and the State Arab schools have been falling. The large majority of the remaining gaps are explained by the objective allocation formula used by the Ministry of Education.

Finally, we consider enrollment in the special education system, and show large increases during the later years of high school, likely in order to improve performance in the Bagrut exams.

Many schools face substantial teacher turnover

Background: In discussions of teacher shortages and turnover, the most common question asked is how many teachers are missing across the education system. Alternatively, one could ask how many teachers are lacking in a particular district, locality, subject, sector, or supervisory authority.

To understand the difference, suppose there are two schools, each with 100 teachers, and 50 teachers from each school switch places. Overall, no teachers are missing. However, the principal, teaching staff, students, and parents at each school face the implications of a 50% turnover rate.

In the graphs: During the years displayed in the figure on the left, the annual rate of departing teachers was generally lower than the rate of new arrivals. The figure on the right divides schools by turnover rates. Schools where the turnover rate was below 15% have an average turnover rate of 9%, while schools with turnover rates exceeding 35% have an average turnover rate of 43%. As seen, at all turnover rate levels, more teachers joined schools in 2023 where they had not taught the previous year, than left their schools (but did not leave the education system). This shows that during the period considered, any teacher shortage — if, indeed, there was one at all — did not worsen.

Departing and incoming teachers

Selected years

Teacher turnover rate

By school, 2022–2023

Source: Nachum Blass, Taub Center, and David Maagan, CBS | Data: CBS, special data analysis

Teacher absenteeism harms students' performance in 5th grade Meitzav exams

Background: Teacher absences may significantly affect educational outcomes.

In the graph: A preliminary examination of the relationship between teacher absenteeism and academic achievements shows that in schools where teacher absence rates are above average, student achievements are lower than in schools where teacher absence rates are below average.

Beyond the graph: If the result is, indeed, causal, it is not surprising, as academic success depends on a stable learning environment and a close, productive relationship between students and their teachers, which is built on familiarity between them. In addition, we believe that a substantial rate of teacher absences negatively affects other educational aspects.

Teacher absenteeism and academic achievement
Teacher absences (hours) per student, 5th grade Meitzav scores

Source: Nachum Blass, Taub Center, and David Maagan, CBS | Data: CBS, special data analysis

And their Bagrut achievements suffer as well

In the graph: Examining the relationship between the average hours of teacher absences per student and achievements in Bagrut exams shows a similar picture to that on the previous page. In the 2021/2022 school year, in schools where the number of absenteeism hours was below average, the average Bagrut score (including bonus points) was 86.9, compared to an average score of 83.0 in schools where the number of absenteeism hours was above average. Similarly, the Bagrut qualification rates were 84% and 75%, respectively.

Beyond the graph: In similar fashion to the discussion on the previous page regarding primary school education, it is highly likely that a high rate of staff absences also impacts students negatively in other areas.

Teacher absenteeism and bagrut achievements
Teacher absences (hours) per student, 2021/2022 school year

Source: Nachum Blass, Taub Center, and David Maagan, CBS | Data: CBS, special data analysis

Dropout rates in high schools were falling in all sectors, but have risen since the COVID-19 pandemic

In the graph: Over the last decade, dropout rates in Grades 9–12 have generally declined across all groups and grade levels. Between 2021 and 2023, a slight increase in dropout rates was measured, though they did not return to pre-COVID-19 levels.

Beyond the graph: In Hebrew education, dropout rates peak in 11th grade, while in Arab education, they are highest in 9th grade. Trends in the State-religious and State (secular) education systems are relatively similar, with most dropping out occurring between 9th and 11th grade, whereas in Haredi education, dropout rates are particularly high in 11th grade due to the transition to advanced yeshivot. (Note that the scale on the graphs for Haredi and State Arab schools are different from those for the State Hebrew and State-religious schools.)

Dropout rates from high school

By grade level and education supervisory authority

Source: Nachum Blass, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

Falling budgetary gaps between State-religious and State Hebrew schools; rising gaps between State Arab and State Hebrew schools

Background: There are budgetary gaps in per-class and per-student funding in the official primary regular school system, and the question is what is the source of the existing gaps, and have they been narrowing?

In the graph: The graph shows funding gaps after controlling for school characteristics. The gap in per-class funding between State-religious and State Hebrew primary education narrowed from about 5% at the beginning of the period to less than 2% in recent years. Per-student funding shows a similar trend: the gap narrowed from about 9% to less than 3%. In the Arab sector, funding is the lowest: the per-class funding gap compared to State Hebrew education grew from about 7% to about 10%, and the per-student gap grew from about 6% to about 9%.

Overall, considering the variables included in the funding model, the gaps between State-religious and State (Hebrew and Arab) primary education have narrowed over time, both for per-class and per-student funding. This finding is consistent with the high school data presented in *A Picture of the Nation 2024*.

Source: Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

The majority of the budgetary gap stems from the budgetary formula

In the graph: Much of the variation in class and per-student funding (shown on the previous page) is linked to variables built into the funding formula — such as school size, the Nurture Index, participation in the long school day program, and the presence of special education classes. Unexplained variation is higher for per-class funding (35%–43% over the years) than for per-student funding (21%–29%).

Per-class funding highlights the combined weight of variables reflecting differential funding principles that compensate schools serving lower socioeconomic communities. For example, the Nurture Index, long school day, and the locality's socioeconomic cluster together account for 37%–48% of the variation over time. For per-student funding, school size, and special education classes have the greatest impact.

Sector and supervisory authority type contribute little to either model, and their effect has declined over time from 7.9% to 4.3% per class and from 7.8% to 3.2% per student. In sum, the funding formula reflects educational and social priorities, and different formulae can yield different outcomes.

Sources of budgetary differences between schooling streams

Source: Nachum Blass and Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

There is a large transfer of students from regular schools to special education schools in 12th grade

Background: Discussion of special education in Israel usually looks at the system as a whole. However, to understand the trends fully, it is important to examine them by education level. The common belief is that most of the growth in special education enrollment happens in the early years — kindergarten and primary school — based on the assumption that at later stages, the number of students with special needs stabilizes because issues are already identified, solutions are in place (even if partially), and diagnosed students are integrated as much as possible into regular education.

In the graphs: A closer look at the data reveals a very different picture, though. The left graph shows that from Grade 1 to Grade 12, the number of students in each cohort decreases. Reasons include dropouts and transfers to special education settings. The graph on the right shows a steady rise in the number of students attending separate special education schools, except for a drop when moving from middle to high school. This trend has intensified in recent years. The explanation for this appears on the next page.

Number of students in regular and special education

Source: Nachum Blass and Sarit Silverman, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

There is a dive in the number of students in separate special education classes in regular schools in 10th grade

In the graph: Looking at the number of students in separate classes within regular schools shows a slightly different pattern. In primary school, the number rises steadily; in middle school, it levels off; at the start of Grade 10, it drops sharply, then rises again in Grades 11 and 12.

Beyond the graph: What explains the steady increase in the number of special education students, which contrasts with the trend in regular education? It is often attributed to changes in definitions, late diagnoses, reduced social stigma, and benefits for students and parents when children are classified as having special needs. However, these factors are more relevant for younger ages and do not fully explain the increase in high school.

We believe the main reason is the desire to obtain exam accommodations for matriculation without needing school or district committee approval. Many educators support this view.

Number of students in special classes in regular schools
By year of entrance to first grade

Source: Nachum Blass and Sarit Silverman, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Education

Public spending on higher education in Israel is low relative to the OECD average

Background: Public spending on higher education in Israel totaled approximately NIS 12 billion in the 2023 budget, which is about 0.7% of GDP.

In the graph: In 2020, this expenditure per student in Israel was \$8,526 (PPP-adjusted), significantly below the OECD average of \$14,039. This figure places Israel behind most comparable countries, including welfare states considered to be generous like Sweden, Norway, and Denmark, as well as conservative welfare states such as France and Germany. Even liberal welfare states, such as that of the United States, invest more per student than Israel.

Public spending on higher education
Per-student allocation, dollars, PPP-adjusted, 2020

Note: Expenditure on higher education for academic degree students. In the US, this includes post-secondary education programs lasting two years or more.

Source: John Gal and Shavit Ben-Porat, Taub Center | Data: OECD

Early Childhood

To examine the status of young children in Israel and their parents during the war, the Taub Center's Initiative on Early Childhood Development and Inequality conducted an Online survey among parents of children aged 0–6. The survey was conducted in three waves: the first wave, in January 2024, included 1,199 Jewish parents (either the mother or the father); the second wave, in July 2024, included 804 Jewish respondents who had participated in the first wave (approximately 67% of the initial respondents) and 151 Arab parents; and the third wave, in January 2025, included 801 returning respondents — 720 Jewish participants from the first wave and 82 Arab participants from the second wave. Altogether, 1,350 parents of young children responded to the survey.

The survey relied on self-reported data from parents about their own condition and that of their young children. Its purpose was to assess the emotional, behavioral, and developmental status of young children during this period, as well as their emotional state, and to examine various factors that might explain the findings. This section presents some preliminary results from the third wave of the survey and compares them to the results from the first two waves, highlighting changes seen between January 2024 and 2025.

In addition, we present an analysis of delayed language milestone attainment among young children, based upon data from Tipat Halav (Family Care Centers).

A decrease in emotional difficulties among young children as the war in Gaza progressed

Background: Ongoing exposure to emergency situations can harm children’s emotional and behavioral well-being. Tracking changes in well-being over time is essential for understanding the war’s impact on children and identifying critical times for intervention. Children’s emotional and behavioral difficulties were measured using the Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ), a validated and widely used research tool.

In the graph: The graph shows the average SDQ score for young children across three survey waves. In the first wave (January 2024), shortly after the war began, the average score was significantly higher than in the second wave (July 2024). Between the second and third waves (January 2025), there was no significant further change.

Beyond the graph: The findings show that the main impact on young children occurred at the start of the war, with difficulties later declining and stabilizing. However, it is important to keep monitoring these children and provide support even after the initial emotional strain decreases.

Average level of emotional and behavioral difficulties among young children
SDQ index, by survey wave

Note: Based on parental reporting in survey. The I-bars represent 95% confidence intervals.

Source: Blank et al., Taub Center

Depression, anxiety, and stress among parents of young children declined as the war in Gaza continued

Background: The security situation in Israel since October 7 has significantly affected the mental well-being of parents of young children. To assess their distress levels, we used the DASS scale — a standard tool for measuring depression, anxiety, and stress in adults, widely used in psychological research to provide an overall picture of mental health and responses to stress.

In the graph: The graph shows the average total DASS score (combining depression, anxiety, and stress) for parents of young children across three survey waves. In the first wave, parents reported particularly high levels of distress. The second wave showed a drop, and the third wave showed a further, much larger decline, reaching the lowest level recorded so far.

Beyond the graph: The findings indicate that the decline in parental distress takes time. A significant drop in depression, anxiety, and stress levels was seen only after a year, showing that adjustment to a prolonged emergency is gradual.

Average level of symptoms of depression, anxiety, and stress among parents of young children
DASS index, by survey wave

Note: Based on parental reporting in survey. The I-bars represent 95% confidence intervals.

Source: Blank et al., Taub Center

Higher levels of depression and anxiety among Arabs

In the graph: According to the January 2025 survey, the average scores for the three DASS components show clear gaps between Jewish and Arab parents, especially in anxiety and depression. Arab parents report higher levels of anxiety and depression than Jewish parents. However, there are no significant differences in stress levels between the two groups, and parents overall report relatively high stress.

Beyond the graph: The differences in anxiety and depression may reflect the war's varying impacts on different population groups in Israel. Arab parents may feel less secure, particularly given the security situation in their areas. At the same time, the lack of a significant difference in stress suggests that all parents, regardless of ethnicity, share the mental burden of wartime, while anxiety and depression are more influenced by social and cultural factors. Other factors, such as the rise in homicide rates within the Arab community and fluctuations in employment, may also contribute to their more complex mental state. Therefore, caution is needed when attributing higher distress levels solely to the war.

Average levels of depression, anxiety, and stress among parents of young children
DASS index, survey third wave, by sector

Note: Based on parental reporting in survey. The I-bars represent 95% confidence intervals.

Source: Blank et al., Taub Center

School closures initially led to more emotional and behavioral difficulties

Background: During the war, educational settings were closed for varying lengths of time, which may have affected children’s emotional and behavioral development.

In the graph: The average total SDQ score for children across the three survey waves shows a clear pattern: children whose educational settings were closed for more than two weeks experienced more difficulties than those whose settings were closed for up to two weeks. In the second and third waves, the level of difficulties dropped significantly, and no clear differences remained between the groups based on closure duration.

Beyond the graph: Children who stayed home for more than two weeks likely faced greater challenges due to disruption of routine and lack of educational and emotional support. However, the improvement in later waves suggests that children and their families adapted to the new reality and may have found alternative solutions. The findings show that while closing educational settings in emergencies can have an immediate impact on children’s emotional state, the effect does not persist over time.

Average level of emotional and behavioral difficulties
SDQ index, by length of school closures and survey wave

Note: Based on parental reporting in survey. The I-bars represent 95% confidence intervals.

Source: Blank et al., Taub Center

More economic harm from the war to Arabs than to Jews

Background: Household income affects families' economic and mental well-being, especially during times of crisis. During the war, many families in Israel experienced a drop in income and increased financial hardship.

In the graph: The share of Arab families reporting a decrease in household income was higher than that of Jewish families. About 31% of Arab families reported a slight decrease and 16% reported a large decrease. In comparison, only 17% of Jewish families reported a slight decrease and 7% a large decrease.

Beyond the graph: These gaps highlight the particular vulnerability of Arab families during the war and show that the economic impact on them was not due only to the general security situation. Given the significant challenges, these families should receive appropriate support from social and economic frameworks.

Change in family income since January 2024

Note: Based on parental reporting in survey.
Source: Blank et al., Taub Center

Delays in language milestone attainment by young children fall with mother’s education level

In the graph: The series of graphs displays the percentage of children with delayed language milestone attainment, stratified by assessment year, age group, and maternal education. Across the years and age groups, there is a significant inverse relationship between maternal education and delayed milestone attainment: as maternal education level decreases, the rates of delayed milestone attainment increase. This inverse relationship strengthens with increasing age: the gap in delayed milestone attainment between children with low versus high maternal education was found to be largest among the 2–3-year-old children, compared to the 0–1 and 1–2 age groups.

In addition to the effect of maternal education, the graphs reveal a worrying temporal trend: with every successive year, the percentage of children with delayed language milestone attainment increases, and this trend is most evident among children of lower-educated mothers. These trends began before 2020, and the slope is relatively stable throughout the observation years, suggesting that this trend is not related to the COVID-19 period of lockdowns and increased parental stress.

Note: The I-bars represent 95% confidence intervals.
Source: Akiva et al., KI Institute and Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Health

Environment and Health

The graphs in this section address three issues. The first deals with an unfortunate side effect of Israel's incredible desalination infrastructure — the removal of critical minerals from the water, one of which is magnesium. We then turn to the waste crisis in Israel, with a focus on the greenhouse gas methane emitted from waste landfills and from illegal waste burning, and tree felling, where the presence of trees both within and outside urban areas is essential for combating climate change and mitigating the health consequences of rising temperatures.

Large savings in medical costs would result from adding magnesium to desalinated water

Background: To overcome decades-long water shortages, Israel shifted to large-scale desalination. While a technological triumph, this has some undesirable medical consequences due to seawater demineralization. Calcium is the only mineral reintroduced, as purely demineralized water is unfit for drinking. Adding magnesium would entail additional costs.

In the graph: The figure shows estimated cost savings from the expected reduction in type 2 diabetes (T2D) if magnesium were added. As shown, savings rise with higher magnesium intake, higher direct medical cost ratios for T2D vs. non-T2D individuals, and better T2D management. At a minimum, Israel's medical system would save NIS 850 million per cohort's lifetime.

Beyond the graph: Magnesium deficiency persists across all age groups, with those over 65 consuming about 40% of the recommended intake. Besides lowering T2D incidence, higher magnesium intake would yield additional health benefits, including reduced ischemic stroke incidence.

Direct medical cost savings from raising magnesium consumption by 50 mg per day

NIS million, 2019 incidence levels

Note: The ratio of medical costs between individuals with and those without diabetes.

Source: Sadeh, Grotto, Davidovitch, and Weinreb, Taub Center | Data: IHME, 2023; Leal et al., 2009; Weinreb et al. (2024); Zhao et al., 2020

Extensive landfills in Israel lead to growing methane emissions

Background: One of the most severe consequences of waste burial (both legal and illegal) is the emission of methane. Methane (CH₄) is a greenhouse gas with a particularly high warming potential and is a major contributor to climate change. According to estimates, in 2020, atmospheric methane accounted for about 20% of the increase in global temperatures. In addition to its role in climate change, methane also contributes to the formation of a tropospheric ozone layer (near the earth's surface), which is a harmful air pollutant with severe impacts on the respiratory system.

In the graph: In Israel, methane emissions are primarily the result of the growing volume of waste sent to landfills and wastewater treatment facilities. The graphs show that methane emissions in Israel are increasing in a fairly linear fashion and are closely linked to the volume of waste buried (right graph), which itself is driven by population growth (left graph).

Beyond the graph: Growing methane emissions in Israel are not surprising given Israel's failure in dealing with the ongoing solid waste crisis and the continuous increase in solid waste. Interestingly, carbon dioxide emissions have not been increasing.

Volume of waste in landfill, population growth, and methane emissions

2014–2022

Volume of waste in landfill by population growth

Methane emission levels by volume of waste in landfill

Source: Maya Sadeh, Taub Center and Georgii Medvinsky, Tel Aviv University | Data: CBS

Israel ranks poorly on the Environmental Policy Stringency Index

Background: Achieving Israel's national greenhouse gas reduction targets requires, among other things, an accelerated move to solar power from production using coal and gas, reducing waste production, establishing recycling, waste separation, and compost facilities, and subsidizing electricity production from biogas. A monitoring report by Israel's Ministry of Environmental Protection reveals delays in implementing a significant portion of the government's planned policy measures.

In the graph: The delay in implementing government policy is reflected in Israel's score on the Environmental Policy Stringency (EPS) Index. This index measures the extent to which environmental policy measures are implemented, focusing on emissions reduction and climate change preparedness. Scores on the index range from 0 to 6, where "0" indicates no or lenient policies, and "6" indicates stringent and rigorous policies. Compared to other Mediterranean countries, Israel ranks among the lowest in environmental policy implementation, second only to Türkiye. Notably, countries with higher scores on the EPS index demonstrate better environmental performance in practice.

Note: Comparison countries are those with a similar climate to Israel.
Source: Maya Sadeh and Or Siman-Tov, Taub Center | Data: OECD

Nearly a quarter of a million trees were felled between 2021 and 2023

Background: According to a recent OECD report, Israel is among the leading countries in the loss of open spaces for development purposes. While Israel's rapid population growth necessitates the construction of residential buildings and the expansion of infrastructure, the prevalent planning approach favors low-density, isolated neighborhoods on undeveloped land, despite a declared policy to prioritize densifying existing urban areas.

In the graph: These trends are reflected in tree-felling permits. Between 2021 and 2023, permits were issued for the felling of approximately 242,000 trees. The leading cities in tree felling are Rishon LeZion (10,695), Tel Aviv (10,346), and Jerusalem (8,253). These same cities also felled the most trees relative to their tree inventory. In some cities, there is significant variation between years, likely corresponding to the timelines of new neighborhood construction projects.

Beyond the graph: It is now widely understood that due to their importance to healthy ecosystems, thermal comfort, and physical and mental health, mature, full-grown trees are essential infrastructure, on par with water and electricity supply, roads, and pavements.

Average annual tree felling for construction and infrastructure
By percent of tree cover, 2021–2023

Note: Cities selected are those with a municipal forestry officer.
Source: Maya Sadeh and Or Siman-Tov, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security

The vast majority of tree felling is for construction purposes

Background: Tree-felling of mature trees in Israel requires a permit (there are some exceptions, for example, invasive species and agricultural reasons), which is provided by municipal forestry officers in the 16 largest cities, while in the rest of the country they are provided by Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security regional forestry officers. If a tree represents a safety concern (for example, due to proximity to electricity lines) or health hazard (severe allergies), it is not possible to appeal forestry officers' decisions.

In the graph: Most tree-felling is due to housing and infrastructure construction, but the share of safety reasons for which public appeal is not possible has risen to almost 25% of the total, possibly requiring a closer look into the regulations and procedure.

Beyond the graph: Of the 242,000 trees cut down between 2021–2023, 180,000 — 75% were given by six regional forestry officers, and the remaining 25% by 16 municipal officers.

Tree felling by reason

Note: Excluding agriculture and tree felling by the Jewish National Fund.
 Source: Maya Sadeh and Or Siman-Tov, Taub Center | Data: Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security

Demography

The ongoing war has shifted demographic behavior in Israel. In 2024, there were some early signs of an uptick in out-migration rates alongside a mild increase in Jewish women's fertility, which had fallen from 2018–2023. These two factors helped push Israel's growth rate down to 1.1% in 2024. This is Israel's lowest annual growth rate on record, though it remains high by international standards.

Israel's population now exceeds 10 million

In the graph: In September 2024, Israel's *de jure* population, that is, the population that officially lives within the Green Line and in Israeli towns and settlements in Judea/Samaria, passed the 10-million mark. Around 9.81 million are citizens, of whom 2.1 million are Arab, and 480,000, referred to as "Other," are not *halachically* Jewish. In addition, Israel houses more than 200,000 labor migrants and foreign students. These have only been counted separately by Israel's Central Bureau of Statistics since 2023.

Beyond the graph: The growth in the non-Jewish (halachically) and non-Arab populations is now the main factor driving down the percent Jewish in Israel's population. Almost all the Other are what some scholars call *sociologically Jewish*. That is, they live in Jewish neighborhoods and are fully integrated into Israeli life-course, from school to military service and the labor force.

Source: Alex Weinreb, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Israel's long-term and projected growth rate remains very high

Background: Despite its unusually low population growth in 2024, Israel's projected growth remains very high by international standards.

To illustrate how much it deviates from normal patterns in high-income countries, we selected a number of wealthy OECD countries and then indexed each one's population up to 2048 — the 2024–2048 are based on population projections of the UN Population Prospects — relative to the population in 1978.

In the graph: Israel's population in 2048 is projected to be more than 4 times the size of its 1978 population. Even in high-growth Australia, the population will only be 2.2 times that of 1978. In many European and East Asian countries, the population has increased over the last 50 years, but is now, after a few decades of below-replacement fertility, starting to shrink, and to age at a much faster rate than in Israel.

Beyond the graph: Israel's high rates of growth underscore the different constraints facing Israeli policy makers, though it also affords them a set of options — anything related to the large younger cohorts — that many of their counterparts long for.

Source: Alex Weinreb, Taub Center | Data: CBS (Israel); UN Population Prospects (all other countries)

Israel has experienced baby booms after previous wars

Background: Post-war *baby booms* — or *bumps*, if smaller — can be caused by one of two things. The end of war either increases people’s desire for children, or it reduces the amount of time a couple is separated, raising the frequency of sex and the likelihood of conception. Without specific data, it is not easy to identify the primary cause in many post-war baby booms.

In the graph: Israel experienced post-war baby booms after both the Six-Day War and the Yom Kippur War. Israel’s fertility rate was lower in those years than in prior years. Yet for at least three years following those two wars, fertility rates were higher.

Beyond the graph: The apparent fertility-related effects of the First Lebanon War were more complicated, in part because fertility was already rising in the initial year of war, and in part because the war was much more drawn out.

Total Fertility Rates (TFR) among Jewish women in Israel

Note: Period Total Fertility Rates. This is the average number of children born to a woman in her lifetime given age-specific fertility rates in that year.

Source: Alex Weinreb, Taub Center | Data: CBS

The impact of the October 7th War on fertility rates

Background: Israel entered the war in a context of falling fertility across all populations and all levels of religiosity.

In the graph: In the Muslim population, fertility has fallen steadily and rapidly since the early 2000s. The war did not interrupt this trend in 2024.

In the Jewish population, there are signs that the war has had a pronatalist effect. After stabilizing above 3.1 children per woman in the 2011–2018 period, Jewish women’s fertility was around 3.0 in 2020–2023 (aside from the exceptional COVID year, 2021). In 2024, it climbed again to around 3.07. That is not a large increase, but it is arguably at least 0.1 children higher than it would have been.

Beyond the graph: Data are not yet available that allow us to see if this effect can be seen across all sectors of the Jewish population, or if it is driven by a shift in fertility rates in only some sectors.

Source: Alex Weinreb, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Fertility was higher in all populations — especially among Jews — from August 2024

In the graph: In January and February, 2024, Jewish women's fertility was marginally higher than in 2022 and 2023. From March–May it was at around the same level, and it was notably lower in June and July. This is to be expected given that births in these months were, on average, conceived during the largest waves of reserve duty in October and November, 2023. However, from August until the end of the year, Jewish women's fertility rate was considerably above its 2022–2023 levels, especially in September and October.

There is no sign of an equivalent reduction in fertility in June–July in the Druze and religiously unaffiliated populations — despite men from these populations also being drafted into reserve military duty. However, Druze women's fertility rates in the remaining months of 2024 were equivalent to those of 2022–2023, unlike their fertility rates in the first half of the year. That hints at a mild boost. Similar hints of a late-2024 boost can be seen among Israel's Christian women.

Among Muslims, monthly fertility rates in the second half of 2024 were broadly similar to those of 2023, a sign that the ongoing reduction in Muslim TFR described on the last page was driven by fertility in January–July.

Beyond the graph: Fertility in 2025 will largely reflect conceptions during 2024. That is where we will see clearer signs of the long-term effects of the current war on Israeli fertility rates.

Annualized monthly fertility rates (graphs) and total annual rate (table)

By religion

— 2022 — 2023 — 2024

Jews

Muslims

Christians

Druze

Other

	2022	2023	2024
Jews	3.03	3.00	3.07
Muslims	2.91	2.79	2.71
Christians	1.68	1.59	1.56
Druze	1.85	1.74	1.63
Other	1.26	1.26	1.24

Source: Alex Weinreb, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Seasonal travel patterns of Israelis were different in 2024

In the graph: Israelis' exits from, and entries into, the country have distinct seasonal patterns. There are large net exits in June–July, compensating entries in August, as well as smaller exits around Pesach (March–April) and the High Holidays (September), with compensating entries in May and October.

Two things stand out in 2024. First, 250,000 more Israelis left than entered the country in June–July, much more than in any previous year — the prior record, 180,000, was set in 2018. Second, net entries in August and October were much lower than in prior (non-COVID) years, amounting to only 131,000.

Beyond the graph: Larger June–July exits are consistent with families leaving Israel during the school holidays. By next year we will know more about how many stayed overseas.

Israeli citizens' net movements in and out of the country

Thousands, by month

Source: Alex Weinreb, Taub Center | Data: CBS

More Israelis are leaving Israel but we don't know who they are

In the graph: In 2024, the net number of exits of Israelis (out of Israel) relative to their entries grew substantially in comparison to past years. We do not yet know the extent to which the movement reflects: (a) Israelis normally resident outside Israel who returned in October and November of 2023; (b) a portion of the very large wave of war-driven *aliya* (immigration of Jews to Israel) from Russia and Ukraine choosing to leave; (c) Israelis leaving for long-term travel (e.g., post-army), having delayed it because of COVID-19 or the war; or (d), most worrying, native Israelis choosing to *relocate*, that is, live elsewhere.

In the meantime, the number of olim in 2024 returned to its 2016–2019 range above 30,000.

Annual net entry/exit of Israelis and new immigrants

Source: Alex Weinreb, Taub Center | Data: CBS

There has been an increase in the average age of olim

Background: Migration rates peak from people's early 20s to their early 30s. In the 2017–2020 period that was also true of *aliya*.

In the graph: Over the last few years there has been an increase in the proportion of olim (those making *aliya*) who are in their prime working ages: the number of 35–44-year-olds now matches the number aged 25–34; and 45–54-year-olds now match those aged 5–14 or 15–24 — the two latter typically include the children of the former. The proportion immigrating below age 5 has also been falling.

Beyond the graph: These shifts reflect patterns of falling fertility and aging in global Jewish communities. They also have implications for labor and housing market prospects in Israel, since they suggest that current olim come with more established skill sets and more financial capital than their predecessors.

Age at immigration to Israel

Source: Alex Weinreb, Taub Center | Data: CBS

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